

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDY HABITS, TIME MANAGEMENT AND
ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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Introduction:

To be a successful person in the world it is not only the intelligence but also the intrinsic urge and certain skills are important. Today, life has become very stressful therefore it is extremely important to take out time for self and identify ones strengths and weaknesses and develop a plan for improving the qualities which enhances the performance. Achievement motivation is extremely necessary as it works like catalyst to perform in any area of work. The time management skills occupies prime position in technological era as it help in avoiding stress and increasing efficiency. The study habit plays important role in the process of learning and hence it was felt important to study the relationship between these variables.

Need of the study:

The review of related studies on Study habits, Time Management and Achievement Motivation reveals that the studies conducted on study habits and attitude towards learning, learning skills, achievement in different subjects, locus of control, anxiety are of co-relational type. The studies on time management are in relation to the achievement, student effectiveness, time management strategies of students. The achievement motivation has been studied in relation to gender, academic achievement of students belonging to different categories.

It is interesting to study the relationship between study habits, achievement motivation and time management of students. The findings will be helpful to understand the relationship and formulate the strategies to enhance these skills which are very essential.

Title of the Study: A study of Relationship between Study habits, Time management and Achievement Motivation of Secondary School students.

Operational definition:

Study habit:

it is the methodology adopted by the student to do daily studies.

Time management:

it is planning of available time and its implementation for academic activities by the students.

Achievement motivation:

it is the student's ability to take risk, formulate goal and achieve them.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the relationship between study habits and time management of total sample of students of standard ninth.
2. To study the relationship between study habits and time management of boys of standard ninth.
3. To study the relationship between study habits and time management of girls of standard ninth.
4. To study the relationship between study habits and achievement motivation of total sample of students of standard ninth.
5. To study the relationship between study habits and achievement motivation of boys of standard ninth.
6. To study the relationship between study habits and achievement motivation of girls of standard ninth.
7. To study the relationship between time management and achievement motivation of total sample of students of standard ninth.
8. To study the relationship between time management and achievement motivation of boys of standard ninth.
9. To study the relationship between time management and achievement motivation of girls of standard ninth.

Hypotheses of the Study:

1. There is no significant relationship between study habits and time management of total sample of students of standard ninth.
2. There is no significant relationship between study habits and time management of boys of standard ninth.
3. There is no significant relationship between study habits and time management of girls of standard ninth.
4. There is no significant relationship between study habits and achievement motivation of total sample of students of standard ninth.
5. There is no significant relationship between study habits and achievement motivation of boys of standard ninth.
6. There is no significant relationship between study habits and achievement motivation of girls of standard ninth.
7. There is no significant relationship between time management and achievement motivation of total sample of students of standard ninth.
8. There is no significant relationship between time management and achievement motivation of boys of standard ninth.
9. There is no significant relationship between time management and achievement motivation of girls of standard ninth.

Methodology of the Study:

The study deal with the relationship between study habits and achievement motivation, time management of secondary students' hence descriptive method of co relational type has been used.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study:

The present study dealt with secondary school students of standard IXth. It was thought that these students know what they want, why they have to study and what they want in further life so they have developed their time management skill along with the set of study habits and achievement motivation help for their performance.

Tools of the Research:

The following tools were used for data collection.

1. Personal data sheet.

The personal data sheet has been used to collect personal information.

2. Rating scales to measure.

i) Study habit scale- by Dr. Palsane.

ii) Achievement motivation scale- by Ms.Bapat A.

iii) Time management scale- by Kolwadkar A.

Sample of the study:

For the present study 502 students of standard IXth were selected randomly. There were 246 boys and 256 girls. At first level schools were selected randomly. The students were selected randomly at the second level.

Data collection:

The data has been collected from students by the researcher after taking prior permission of the principals of schools.

Analysis of data:

The data has been analyzed statistically.

Descriptive analysis: measures of central tendencies and measures of variability have been calculated.

Inferential analysis: Pearson's product moment coefficient of correlation has been calculated to study the relationship between the variables.

The relationship between the variables is given in the following table.

Table 1.1

Significance of relationship between Study habits and Time management of Total sample, Boys and Girls.

variables	group	Obtained r	r at 0.05	r at 0.01	L.O.S.
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Study habit & Time management	TSS	0.566	0.088	0.115	0.01
Study habit & Time management	Boys	0.605	0.139	0.182	0.01
Study habit & Time management	Girls	0.556	0.139	0.182	0.01

There is a significant relationship between Study habits and time management of Total sample, Boys and Girls at 0.01 level as the obtained values are greater than 0.115 in case of TSS, and greater than 0.182 in case of boys and girls. This relationship is positive and moderate in magnitude.

Table 1.2

Significant relationship between Study habits and Achievement motivation of total sample of students, Boys and Girls.

Variables	group	Obtained r	r at 0.05	r at 0.01	L.O.S
Study habit & Achieve. motivation	TSS	0.492	0.088	0.115	0.01
Study habit & Achieve. Motivation.	Boys	0.605	0.139	0.182	0.01
Study habit & Achieve. Motivation.	Girls	0.34	0.139	0.182	0.01

There is a significant relationship between Study habits and Achievement motivation of Total sample, Boys and Girls at 0.01 level as the obtained values are greater than 0.115 in case of TSS, and greater than 0.182 in case of boys and girls. This relationship is positive and moderate in magnitude in case of total sample of students and boys while it is low in case of girls.

Table 1.3

Significance of relationship between Time management and

Achievement motivation of Total sample, Boys and Girls.

variables	group	Obtained r	r at 0.05	r at 0.01	L.O.S
Time Mgt & Achieve. motivation	TSS	0.551	0.088	0.115	0.01
Time Mgt & Achieve. Motivation.	Boys	0.64	0.139	0.182	0.01
Time Mgt & Achieve. Motivation.	Girls	0.42	0.139	0.182	0.01

There is a significant relationship between time management and Achievement motivation of Total sample, Boys and Girls at 0.01 level as the obtained r values are greater than 0.115 in case of TSS, and greater than 0.182 in case of boys and girls. This relationship is positive and moderate in magnitude.

Findings of the study:

1. There is a significant positive relationship between Study habits and time management of Total sample, Boys and Girls. It means that the students who plan time properly and implement accordingly are utilizing available time systematically for completing studies.
2. There is a significant, positive relationship between Study habits and Achievement motivation of Total sample, Boys and Girls. This indicates that the students with high achievement motivation are better in planning and utilizing their study time.
3. There is a significant, positive relationship between time management and Achievement motivation of Total sample, Boys and Girls. It can be said that more is the achievement motivation better is time management skills.
Thus, it can be said that the achievement motivation and time management are associated with study habits.

Discussion:

The achievement motivation is a trait of a personality which help individual to set goal and to achieve it. These are ninth standard students who are aware about their future and accordingly set goal and work towards its accomplishment. While achieving they have to plan time in such a way that they can use it optimally. Hence these variables are positively associated.

Suggestions:

Following are the suggestions made on the basis of the findings of the study.

- Teacher should help in formulating goal.
- Teacher and parents can give them a task of keeping the record of time and analyze it.
- Various reward system can be developed in consultation with them so that motivation can be enhanced.
- A positive, constructive feedback provided can help to plan and use study time effectively.

References:

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